

Rubiadin. Part I. Synthesis of 1-Methyl-2:4-dioxy-anthraquinone.

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Rubiadin was first isolated and studied by Schunck and Marchlewski (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 969). They obtained it by the hydrolysis of rubiadin-glucoside, which occurs in madder-root, *Rubia Tinctorum*. It is a lustrous yellow substance, m.p. 290° and sublimes unchanged when heated further. The analysis of the substance as well as the molecular weight determination by Raoult's method agree with the formula $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$. It is an anthraquinone derivative and closely resembles purpuroxanthin as revealed by spectroscopic examination. This leads to the conclusion that rubiadin is a methylated purpuroxanthin. The absence of any methoxy group points to the methyl group being contained in the nucleus. Again since on oxidation phthalic acid is obtained (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 18), the methyl and hydroxyl groups must lie in the same benzene ring of the anthraquinone complex. This restricts the choice of a formula for rubiadin between (1) 2-methyl-1:3-dioxy-anthraquinone and (2) 1-methyl-2:4-dioxy-anthraquinone. Schunck and Marchlewski synthesised (1) by condensing 2:6-dioxy-*paratoluic* acid with benzoic acid in presence of sulphuric acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 183) and obtained a substance melting at 282° and when quickly heated at 290° and giving an acetyl derivative, m.p. 217°-218°. Rubiadin melts at 290° and its acetyl derivative melts at 225°. On these grounds Schunck and Marchlewski gave formula (2) to rubiadin.

The main object of the work was to verify this by actual synthesis.

Fritsch has found that 3-methoxybenzoic acid methyl ester (*Annalen*, 1897, 296, 344) and methyl 2:3-dimethoxy benzoate (*Annalen*, 1898, 301, 352) condense readily with chloral in presence of sulphuric acid to give trichloromethyl phthalides, from which the corresponding phthalic acids may be easily prepared. The reaction

has been successfully applied by Meldrum and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1712; 1920, 117, 964; 1921, 119, 201) for converting oxybenzoic acids to the corresponding phthalic acids.

Our object was to apply this reaction to 2-methyl-3:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid methyl ester with a view to prepare the corresponding phthalic acid, $C_6H(CH_3)(OCH_3)_2(COOH)_2$. The anhydride of this acid on condensation with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and subsequent ring closing with sulphuric acid was expected to give 1-methyl-2:4-dimethoxyanthraquinone, the demethylation product of which would have the constitution ascribed to rubiadin by Schunck and Marchlewski. It was found that the reaction proceeds fairly smoothly up to the phthalide,

The phthalides can be prepared from phenolic ether acids directly by condensing with formaldehyde in presence of hydrochloric acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 195) and this method was employed for preparing large quantities of phthalide from cresorsellenic acid for oxidation experiments. All our attempts to oxidise the phthalide to the corresponding phthalic acid have, however, so far, failed.

We next had recourse to another method of preparation of anthraquinone derivative for our present purpose. 3:5-Oxybenzoic acid condenses with *p*-toluic acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 1141) and 4-methyl-3:5-dioxybenzoic acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 182) and 3:5-dioxybenzoic acid (*Annalen*, 1887, 241, 266) condense with benzoic acid in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid to give rise to the corresponding anthraquinone derivatives. This method was successfully applied to 2-methyl-3:5-dioxybenzoic acid (cresorsellenic acid) with the result that it is now definitely established that the constitution of rubiadin is not what Schunck and Marchlewski ascribed to it.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Methyl-3:5-dioxybenzoic Acid (Cresorsellenic Acid).—The acid was prepared according to the method of Jacobsen and Wieress (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 1960) with slight modification. *o*-Toluic acid (50 g.) was treated with fuming sulphuric acid (200 g.) containing 65% of

sulphuric anhydride and the reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 160-170° for 12 hours. The fuming sulphuric acid was added in two instalments (150 g. and 50 g.) and the heating was completed in two days. The cold sulphonation product was poured on crushed ice and the disulphonic acid was separated from sulphuric acid as the soluble calcium salt by treatment with calcium carbonate, boiling and filtering. The filtrate was then treated with potassium carbonate, when calcium carbonate was precipitated, and the potassium disulphonate remained in solution. It was concentrated by heating on a bare flame and ultimately evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The yield of the potassium salt was almost theoretical.

The potassium salt—50 g. being taken at a time—was added gradually to three times its weight of fused potassium hydroxide kept in a silver basin at a temperature of 210°, and stirred constantly with a copper tube closed at one end and fitted up with a thermometer, which dipped in melted paraffin kept in the tube. The addition of potassium disulphonate was completed in half an hour and the melt was then heated at 248-250° for another half an hour and then the temperature was gradually raised to 270° when the reaction was complete.

The product of potash fusion was then made into a paste with powdered ice and treated with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The acidified solution thus obtained was then allowed to cool, and was filtered and extracted thrice with ether. Cresorsellenic acid was obtained on evaporation of the ether as a grey coloured solid mass mixed up with tarry matters. The mass was dried on a porous plate and crystallised from water with the addition of animal charcoal when a granular white crystalline product was obtained; m. p. 237-239°. Yield of the substance was 30% of the theoretical.

2-Methyl-3:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (cresorsellenic acid dimethyl ether), prepared with the help of dimethyl sulphate in the usual manner, formed white needle shaped crystals, m. p. 160°. The yield was 90% of the theoretical. (Found: C, 60·91; H, 6·81. $C_{10}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 61·22; H, 6·12 per cent.).

2-Methyl-3:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid methyl ester (methyl ester of cresorsellenic acid dimethyl ether), b. p. 289-291°. (Found: C, 62·55; H, 6·92. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 62·85; H, 6·66 per cent.).

6-Methyl-3:5-dimethoxy-2-trichloromethyl phthalide.—2-Methyl-3:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid methyl ester (5 g.) was mixed with finely powdered chloral hydrate (4 g.) in a stoppered bottle

and cold 90% sulphuric (25 g.) acid was added and the mixture allowed to stand for 24 hours. The reaction was then complete, and the condensation product was found to be a dirty solid mass, which was mixed up with pieces of ice and filtered. The solid mass thus obtained was washed with water and 50% alcohol alternately to remove the unacted reactants and the sulphuric acid. The crude condensation product was then dried on the porous plate and crystallised from methyl or ethyl alcohol. White crystalline mass, m. p. 176°. The yield was theoretical. (Found: Cl, 82.39. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4Cl$, requires Cl, 82.71 per cent.).

6-Methyl-3:5-dimethoxy-2-phthalide carboxylic Acid.

The trichloromethyl phthalide derivative (5 g.) was heated with an excess of 20% caustic soda solution (25 c. c.) on the water-bath with a reflux condenser for 5 hours. The trichlorophthalide dissolved very slowly, ultimately giving a clear homogeneous yellowish liquid. The solution was then cooled and exactly neutralised, and to the neutral solution a very slight excess of hydrochloric acid was added when a tarry matter together with a little of the product of hydrolysis of the trichloromethyl phthalide was thrown down which was filtered off. The filtrate was then acidified with a slight excess of hydrochloric acid and the phthalide carboxylic acid, which was precipitated as sticky white precipitate, was filtered at the pump and dried on the porous plate. It is soluble in water with difficulty but readily in alcohol. It is crystallised repeatedly from water and purified by animal charcoal. White crystalline plates, m. p. 218-219°. Yield, 50%. During an attempt to crystallise the acid from alcohol the ethyl ester melting at 134° was obtained. (Found: C, 52.9; H, 5.5. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$, requires C, 57.14; H, 4.76. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5 \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 53.8; H, 5.1 per cent).

6-Methyl-3:5-dimethoxyphthalide.—Phthalide carboxylic acid (2 g.) was taken in a large test tube fitted with a long air condenser and heated in a sulphuric acid bath at 225-235°. The decomposition of the acid to the phthalide was complete when no more carbon dioxide evolved; but to ensure a complete decomposition it was heated for sometime longer even when the evolution of CO_2 had ceased. A long air condenser was used because the phthalide formed in the process is highly sublimable. The phthalide is slightly soluble in alcohol, but fairly soluble in chloroform. A very suitable solvent for the phthalide is found in acetic acid. It is a very light crystalline white substance melting at 249°. The yield in this process was

as low as 20% of the theoretical. (Found: C, 62.9; H, 5.96. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 68.45; H, 5.76 per cent.) Attempts at oxidation of the phthalide to the corresponding phthalic acid have so far failed.

1-Methyl-2 : 4-dioxyanthraquinone.—2-Methyl-8 : 5-dioxybenzoic acid (oresorsellenic acid, 5 g.) was intimately mixed with pure benzoic acid (50 g.) in a 500 c. c. round bottomed Pyrex flask. To the mixture chemically pure sulphuric acid (25 g.) was added and gently shaken, when a homogeneous red solution was formed. Such a large excess of benzoic acid was used to avoid the self condensation of the oresorsellenic acid. The reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 125—130° for 12 to 15 hours. The heating was completed in 2 days. As the heating was continued the colour of the reaction mixture changed from red to dark-red and ultimately to black. When the reaction was complete, the cold reaction-product was poured on powdered ice, filtered and dried on the porous plate. The product thus obtained contained a large amount of carbonaceous matter from which the substance was separated by extraction with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus. The ether was then removed by distillation, when a brown solid mass of the anthraquinone derivative mixed up with benzoic acid was obtained. The benzoic acid could be removed from the condensation product by steam distillation, but the process was found to be inconvenient because nearly 12 hours were necessary to completely drive away the benzoic acid. By using Na_2CO_3 solution to effect the separation the difficulty was overcome. The self-condensation product of oresorsellenic acid (anthrachryson) contains four (OH) groups, and is much more acidic than the dihydroxyanthraquinone. The crude condensation product was taken in a mortar and triturated with Na_2CO_3 solution which was very gradually added so long as there was evolution of CO_2 . When no further CO_2 evolved a very small quantity of Na_2CO_3 solution was very cautiously added to partially dissolve the anthrachryson, and the substance was separated by filtration. The crude anthraquinone derivative thus obtained was then crystallised two times from benzene when a very beautiful orange crystalline product melting, after sublimation, at 265-266° was obtained. Yield was 4% of the theoretical. (Found: C, 70.52; H, 4.22. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.86; H, 3.80 per cent).

1-Methyl-2 : 4-diacetoxyanthraquinone.—1-Methyl-2 : 4-dioxyanthraquinone (5 g.) was mixed with an excess of freshly distilled acetic anhydride and a few drops of pyridine, and taken in a small conical flask fitted with a long air condenser and heated to

boiling on the sand-bath very gently for an hour and a half, by which time the reaction was complete. The product was then poured into water. The acetyl derivative was at first thrown down as an oily liquid which solidified on cooling. The solid product was then separated by filtration, and purified from associated acetic anhydride and the unacted anthraquinone derivative by repeated treatment with sodium carbonate solution. The product was then washed with cold water to remove the adhering sodium carbonate, dried on the porous plate and purified by crystallisation from alcohol with animal charcoal, when the di-acetyl derivative was obtained as faintly yellowish needle shaped crystals, m. p. 181-182°. (Found: C, 67.49; H, 4.43. $C_{16}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 67.45; H, 4.14 per cent.).

On deacetylation, the original substance meeting at 265-266° was obtained.